

A STUDY OF OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AMONG SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

In a nationwide sample of people at different occupational levels that tension increases with rank and with income. There is relationship between a person's rank in a organization and the amount of pressure from associates. The present study was undertaken to study the Occupational Stress of primary, middle, high and higher secondary teachers who were working in state Government, public/missionary, army and Navovidayalas of Kashmir Valley. For measuring the Occupational Stress by Dr. A.K. Srivastava and Dr. A.P.Singh.was used. The sample of the study consisted of 720 teachers randomly selected from the schools of eight districts of whole Valley. The data was analyzed through mean, S.D, t-test and three way ANOVA. The findings of the study revealed that Age, Qualification ,Experience and Marital status affects the Occupational Stress of teachers.

Key Words: - the Occupational Stress, Strain, Organization

INTRODUCTION

The history of the movement for improving women's status all over the world and especially in India shows emphasis from the beginning on education as the most significant institution for changing women's subjugated position in the society. Increase of educational facilities and opportunities and removal of age old barriers on entry of women to particular streams and levels of education came to be supported by champions of women's emancipation from the 19th century onwards. Social reforms in India also emphasized the crucial importance of education of women to improve their status in society.

Much of group behavior is characterized by the roles members play. One plays different roles at different times, and the display of role behavior in the individual often is determined by social interaction. We can think of role behaviors as being related first to the position we hold in a group or on the job.

Sometimes one is made conscious of lack of identity or status in a group when he takes a look at which things frustrate, where one feels a need to defend, as though when he is being attacked. Often egoistic motives are satisfied by recognition, by status signs, by being admitted into the inner circle, and sometimes one gets his ego hurt by seemingly little things.

It was found in a nationwide sample of people at different occupational levels that tension increases with rank and with income. The gradual increase in tension as one moves upward is

represented by such instances as the proportion of person reporting that pressures on them went up markedly with both the number of persons supervised and the number of levels of subordinates for which they are responsible coordinating the work of others is a factor in management stress, as is the mediation of differences between organizational departments. There is relationship between a person's rank in a organization and the amount of pressure from associates. The primary teachers reported their own feelings of irritability, criticism from inspectors, low status in the society and slow progress of children as being sources of greater degree of worry and strain as compared to high and higher secondary

School teachers mentioned about the continuous noise of the pupils, low results, despite their best efforts, indiscipline of students, inadequate Building and lack of equipment, and disobedient students, as sources of stress and strain. Most teachers reported the noise of children, own feeling of irritability, as source of stress and strain. The urban teachers did not report more worries and strains which occurred more frequently in case of rural teachers.

Occupational stress for the present study is defined operationally as to what extent the female teachers of primary, middle, high/higher secondary schools of Government, public/missionary, army and Navodayas of Kashmir valley experience stresses and strains while playing their dual roles.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

1. To study significance of differences in occupational stress among female teachers belonging to different levels of age (A) levels of school (B) and type of school (C) individually and jointly in different combinations.
2. To study significance of differences in occupational stress among female teachers belonging to different levels of qualification (A) levels of school (B) and type of school (C) individually and jointly in different combinations.
3. To study significance of differences in occupational stress among female teachers belonging to different levels of experience (A) levels of school (B) and type of school (C) individually and jointly in different combinations.
4. To study significance of differences in occupational stress among female teachers belonging to different levels of marital status (A) levels of school (B) and type of school (C) individually and jointly in different combinations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dr. Ansarul Hasan (2014). A Study of Occupational Stress of Primary School Teachers. In the present study an attempt was made to compare teachers' occupational stress of primary government and private school teachers of Tehsil Laksar, District-Haridwar. A sample of 100 teachers was selected, 50 each from government and private schools. Teachers' Occupational

Stress Scale constructed and standardized by Dr. Sajid Jamal and Dr. Abdul Raheem was administered. Findings revealed that in general, the primary school teachers have found to be highly stressed. Moreover, the private primary school teachers have also found to be highly stressed in comparison to their government primary school teacher counterparts. September 2017. Occupational Stress (OS) among teachers predispose to depression and anxiety. No study was done to assess these problems among Egyptian teachers. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of OS, depression and anxiety among Egyptian teachers. A Cross Sectional Study was done on 568 Egyptian teachers. The respondents filled a questionnaire on personal data, and the Arabic version of the Occupational Stress Index (OSI), the Arabic validated versions of Taylor manifest anxiety scale and the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) were used to assess OS, anxiety and depression respectively. The prevalence of OS, anxiety and depression among teachers was (100%, 67.5% and 23.2%) respectively. OS, anxiety and depression scores were significantly higher among teachers with an age more than 40 years, female teachers, primary school teachers, those with inadequate salary, higher teaching experience, higher qualifications and higher workload. A significant weak positive correlation was found between OS scores and anxiety and depression scores. This study indicated the need for future researches to address risk factors of OS and mental disorders among Egyptian teachers, and the need of periodical medical evaluation of teachers and medical and psychological support for the identified cases.

Jasmani Binti Mohd Yunus(2017). Occupational Stressors among Teachers at Secondary School in Perak. The purpose of this study is to present the findings on the stress factors of teachers in Ipoh, Malaysia. Quantitative data were collected via questionnaire distributed amongst teachers in Ipoh. A total of 329 teachers completed the questionnaires. The findings of the research showed that there were significant relationship between occupational stressors and stress. It is interesting to note that hierarchical multiple regression analysis indicated the four dimension of occupational stress namely role overload, work hour, family conflicts, financial factors and work location The research also indicates that three variables work load, hour work, family conflicts have significant relationship with stress while financial factors and work location have no relationship with stress. The variables have significant impact on the teachers stress. The regression analysis showed that there is significant impact between occupational stressors and stress. Keywords: Stress, work load, work hour, financial problem, family conflicts and work.

Monti Tyagi (2016). The study area consists of 1139 secondary school teachers and out of them 321 participants were taken for this study. Again, to select the sample schools, cluster random sampling and then lottery method of simple random sampling techniques were used. All BA holder teachers of the selected sample schools (except the principals and vice principals) were included in the sample size. To collect data for the study, occupational stress inventory, coping-questionnaire and stressor-questionnaire were used. To analyze the collected data, both

descriptive and inferential statistics were applied. Accordingly, the result of the occupational stress inventory indicated that, all the secondary school teachers experienced high level of occupational stress. The dominant stressors were interpersonal related sources, administrative related sources and students"-parents related sources respectively. Besides, the mostly used coping strategy by more than half of the teachers was turning to religion. What is more, the result of this study also indicated that gender, work place and family size have no effect in experiencing occupational stress among the teachers. On the contrary, age and work experience have significant mean difference. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendation was made. The educational bureaus of the central zone and the region, health professionals and other educational practitioners, in collaboration with the schools, should take appropriate measures to reduce the current level of the teachers" occupational stress and to make them use the most effective coping strategies.

Dr. S.S.Jeyaraj (2018). The aim of the study is to determine the Occupational Stress level of Government and Aided Higher Secondary School Teachers living in different socio-cultural and economic situations. The scale used in the study has been developed by researches. 185 Aided school teachers and 120 Government teachers have participated in the present study. At the end of the study it was seen that Aided school teachers have more occupational stress levels than Government school teachers. There is a meaningful difference in the stress level points of Government and Aided Higher Secondary Teachers. Policy makers are advised to analyse the teacher training and assessment system with the assumption that personal and social characteristics and working conditions may have an effect on teacher occupational stress. Results also showed that teachers who reported greater stress were less satisfied with teaching, reported greater frequency of absences and a greater number of total days absent, were more likely to leave teaching (career intention), and less likely to take up a teaching career again (career commitment). Implications for further research are also discussed.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

First of all list of institutions of primary, middle, high/higher secondary schools were prepared. The stratification was done on the basis of type of schools existing at different levels of education in the valley. All schools falling in the category were considered as a population and the stratification was done across the different districts. The total list indicated that the number of all types of schools at all levels of education were very few in some categories so it was decided to select 60 schools of each category

Tool used:

Occupational stress index.

By- Dr. A.K. Srivastava and Dr. A.P.Singh.

DATA ANALYSIS OR EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

After the data was collected by administering occupational stress inventory to each category three way analysis of variance (2x3x4) is used.

The mean differences in occupational stress with reference to different levels of age, levels of school and type of schools in 2x3x4 factorial design are shown in the table:

<i>Source of Variance</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
<i>Variable A</i>	53880.07	1.00	53880.07	25.54 *
<i>Variable B</i>	2104.90	2.00	1052.45	0.50 **
<i>Variable C</i>	13317.08	3.00	4439.03	2.10 *
<i>AxB</i>	227.03	2.00	75.68	0.04 **
<i>AxC</i>	7312.23	3.00	3656.12	1.73 **
<i>BxC</i>	12463.97	6.00	12463.97	5.91 *
<i>AxBxC</i>	17923.37	6.00	2987.23	1.42 **
<i>Within</i>	455761.00	216.00	2110.00	

The mean differences in occupational stress with reference to different levels of qualification, levels of school and type of schools in 2x3x4 factorial design are shown in the table:

<i>Source of Variance</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
<i>Variable A</i>	132117.34	1.00	132117.34	39.21 *
<i>Variable B</i>	11018.63	2.00	5509.32	1.64 **
<i>Variable C</i>	10963.55	3.00	3654.52	1.08 **
<i>AxB</i>	2400.70	2.00	800.23	0.24 **
<i>AxC</i>	3696.08	3.00	1848.04	0.55 **
<i>BxC</i>	31314.97	6.00	31314.97	9.29 *
<i>AxBxC</i>	15341.23	6.00	2556.87	0.76 **
<i>Within</i>	727749.90	216.00	3369.21	

The mean differences in occupational stress with reference to different levels of experience, levels of school and type of schools in 2x3x4 factorial design are shown in the table:

Source of Variance	SS	Df	MS	F
Variable A	2870.42	1.00	2870.42	3.02 *
Variable B	15955.86	2.00	7977.93	8.39 *
Variable C	1869.57	3.00	623.19	0.66 **
AxB	3669.36	2.00	1223.12	1.29 **
AxC	478.42	3.00	239.21	0.25 **
BxC	6719.51	6.00	6719.51	7.07 *
AxBxC	2911.21	6.00	485.20	0.51 **
Within	205348.60	216.00	950.69	

The mean differences in occupational stress with reference to different levels of marital status, levels of school and type of schools in 2x3x4 factorial design are shown in the table:

<i>Source of Variance</i>	SS	Df	MS	F
Variable A	120691.35	1.00	120691.35	128.25 *
variable B	3120.43	2.00	1560.22	1.66 **
Variable C	4411.97	3.00	1470.66	1.56 **
AxB	1600.30	2.00	533.43	0.57 **
AxC	5056.68	3.00	2528.34	2.69 *
BxC	2202.13	6.00	2202.13	2.34 *
AxBxC	987.67	6.00	164.61	0.17 **
Within	203272.40	216.00	941.08	

RESEARCH FINDINGS

1. Age affects the occupational stress of teachers.
2. Qualification affects the occupational stress of teachers.
3. Experience, level of school affects the occupational stress of female teachers and type of school does not affect occupational stress.

4. Marital status affects the occupational stress of teachers, but level and type of school does not affect it.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Age affects the occupational stress of teachers. Level of school does not affect the occupational stress and type of school affect occupational stress of teachers, where as age with level of school and type of school does not affect occupational stress, but level with type of school affects occupational stress. When age, level and type interact with each other it is found that they does not affect occupational stress among female teachers.

2. Qualification affects the occupational stress of teachers. Level and type of school does affects the occupational stress where as qualification with level and type of school does not affect the occupational stress, level with type affect occupational stress. When qualification, level and type interact with each other it is found that they does not affect occupational stress among female teachers.

3. Experience, level of school affects the occupational stress of female teachers and type of school does not affect occupational stress, but occupational stress with level of school and with type of school does not affect occupational stress of teachers, but level with type of school affect occupational stress. When experience, level and type interact with each other it is found that they does not affect occupational stress among female teachers.

4. Marital status affects the occupational stress of teachers, but level and type of school does not affect it. Marital status with level of schools does not affect occupational stress but Marital status with type of schools affects the Marital status, as well as level with type of schools affect occupational stress. When marital status, level and type interact with each other it is found that they does not affect occupational stress among female teachers.

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